

**REVIEW ON: PLANT- BASED NATURAL POLYMER EMPLOYED IN
NOVEL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM AND THEIR APPLICATION****Simpi Sharma*¹ and Kaushikee Singh²**

¹Department of Pharmaceutics, Bhavadiya Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences and
Research, Ayodhya U.P. India.

²Department of Pharmaceutics, Kunwar Haribansh Singh College of Pharmacy Jaunpur,
U.P. India.

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Corresponding Author*Simpi Sharma**

Department of Pharmaceutics,
Bhavadiya Institute of
Pharmaceutical Sciences and
Research, Ayodhya U.P. India.

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ABSTRACT

Active pharmaceutical ingredient and excipient are two essential ingredients of any pharmaceutical dosage form, APIs are the responsible for main pharmacological action, where as excipient used for the manufacturing for the dosage form furthermore improve biocompatibility and physiochemical properties of the various formulation. Polymers are mainly employed for the many years along with the goal of encourage effectiveness and efficiency of the drug. Polymers play important role in the evaluation of drug release technology. Generally natural polymers used as taste making agent, rate controlling agent, protecting and stabilizing in buccal drug delivery system. In recent years, due to many complications associated with the drug release and side effect of synthetic polymer various pharmaceuticals compounds liable towards the natural polymer because there readily admissible body and

highly compatible with and have less or no more side effects. The aim of this review to accommodate a critical overview of the continue research in the field of novel drug delivery system with significance of the involvement of the plant based natural polymers like, fenugreek seed mucilage, karaya gum, flaxseed mucilage, aloe vera gel, inulin, rosin, hibiscus mucilage, tamarind gum and okra gum etc.

KEYWORDS: Polymers, novel drug delivery system, formulation, plant based natural Polymer.

INTRODUCTION

Polymers are the macro- molecules along with repeating mono-metric structural unit i.e. joined covalently.^[1] Natural polymers are the reason for noteworthy present day item. The terms polymer was firstly introduced by Swedish physic. J.J. Berzelius.^[2,3] Polymers often include protein, carbohydrate and fibers.^[2]

The word polymer was derived from the Greek word “Poly” means many and “meros” that means parts or unit of high molecular mass.^[3] Polymers are the giant molecules of high molecular weight called macromolecules which are formed by linking together a large number of small molecules called monomers.^[2] Natural polymers have been emerged as one of the most widely research materials for enhancing the therapeutic effect of the existing API/drug molecules. In compare to synthetic resources of polymer the natural polymers are bio-degradable and bio-compatible and relatively safe and effective.^[3]

General classification of Polymers: *Raheswari et al*

Importance of natural polymers over synthetic polymer

1. Biodegradable

All living organisms are the wide range source of the occurrence of natural polymer. In environment or on the human body they have not show adverse side effect while synthetic polymer have show mild effect because they are prepared from various chemical compound due to which they also show side effect on atmosphere *Rajeswari et al.*

2. Biocompatible and Nontoxic^[2]

As compared to synthetic polymer natural polymers are non toxic and bio compatible with chemically, nearly all of these plant material are carbohydrate in nature and composed of repeating mono-saccharine unit.^[3]

3. Economic

In compare to synthetic polymer the natural polymers are cheaper and their production cost is less.^[1]

4. Safe and devoid of side effect

The natural polymers occur from natural sources hence safe and having no side effect where as synthetic polymers, being prepared by using chemical and have side effect.^[2]

5. Ease to available

In many countries natural polymers are growing in the form of herbs being economical than synthetic polymer, (*Rajeswari et al.*) are having no side effect and keeping in the view their application in many industries they produce in the large quantities. Hence their availability is insured that synthetic polymers.^[3]

Plant based natural polymers and their role in novel drug delivery system

The following plant based natural polymers are being extensively studied their role as facillator in novel drug delivery system-

1. Pectin gum,
2. Guar Gum,
3. Aloevera Gel,
4. Karaya Gum ,
5. Inulin,
6. Rosin Or Colophony,
7. Hibiscus leaves Mucilage,

8. Fenugreek Mucilage,
9. Tamarind Gum,
10. Flaxseed mucilage

PECTIN GUM

Firstly the pectin gum (carbohydrates) was isolated and identified by French chemist Braconnot the mucilage was isolated from the carrot in 1825 in 1790 the scientist Vauquelin noticed that having gel like properties i.e. observed in juice of the apple fruits.^[12] The terms *pectin* abbreviated from the Greek word "*Pektikos*" means to "*Congel*".^[12] On the hydrolysis the inner portion of the citrus peel such as orange, lemon (mostly plant that belonging to family Rutaceae) is the polysaccharides. (B.V. Basavaraj *et al.*) The chief chemical constituents of gum of the pectin is linear poly-saccharides that composed of linked D galacturonic acid residue relating to average molecular weight about fifty thousand to about one lack eighty thousand.^[14] The rich constituents of gum including, rhamnose, arabinose, xylose, glucose and galactose found in galacturonic acid poly saccharides. (B.V. Basavaraj *et al.*) Pectin has been scrutinized as when inactive material (excipients) mixed with the ethyl cellulose employed as a gelling agent, stabilizers muco-adhesive agent. (Mishra *et al.*) In the colon specific drug delivery system it was used as film coating agent, microparticuars system for eye preparation (ophthalmic preparation) and matrix types for the formulation of trans-dermal patches.^[15]

Pectin polymers are that polymer which consist strong potential properties i.e. hydrophilic (water loving) compound. In the preparation of matrix patches of pectin gum along with amides, suitable for formulation of trans-dermal chloro-quinine drug delivery system in accustomed to mask the unpleasant taste or bitter taste when it was given by oral route.^[15]

Extraction of Pectin from citrus fruits: (Mishra *et al.*)

The peel powder of (citrus fruit like lemon or orange) was measured about 30 gram by using weighing machine,^[13] then transfer into a 1 L of (larger) beaker containing ~450 ml of distilled water & ~2ml HCl (hydrochloric acid) was incorporated to give a ph (power of hydrogen) of 1.27 each of the citrus fruits peel samples were than steamed for 1 hours there for after the residues were eliminated from the extracts by filtering through a muslin cloth. the prepared cake (residue) was rinsed with 250ml of boiled distilled water & the combined obtained filtrate was precipitated was allowed to cool refrigerated at temperature 250C to lower the heat degradation of the pectin gum the obtained resulting pectin was extracted

precipitated by the addition of 200ml iso-propanol (95%) and then stirrer the extracted pectin for 30 mint to allow pectin gum float on the upper surface in the beaker.^[13] The gelatinous pectin flocculation were then filter out then resulting pectin gum was rinsed with iso-propanol 200ml and strained out the extracted pectin through the muslin cloth to remove residues of HCl (Hydrochloric acid) & universal salt like compound Sodium chloride then it was to be dried in oven and warehoused in well closed container for further application in NDDS.(Novel drug delivery system)

GUAR GUM

Guar gum also named as guaran, gum cyamopsis, clusterbeanlucern, guarina, glucotard, guaren, guargum is the powder obtained from endosperm seed of the guaran gum plant (guar plant) cymopsis tetragoloba herb Fabaceae or also named as leguminosae family (S. Liyanage *et al.*

Ind. Crop.Prod. Basically guar gum termed as galactomannas having linear polysaccharide consisting at (1-4)-dieluatorially linked BD mannose monomer, some of single sugar side chain of BD galactose attached to it.

The FDA (Food Drug Administration) proclaimed that gaur gum safe for the general purpose use.^[16] In oral extended release drug delivery system; gaur gum latterly been spotlight as a more versatile, extravagantly and flexible carrier. (B.V. McCleary *et al.*)

Gaur gum powder is especially functional for colon delivery considering that it can be profligate by specific enzyme in gastrointestinal tract region.^[17,63] Gaur Gum generally protect the candidate drug from the region of the stomach & small intestine environment i.e. prevent from micro organism and gastric pH (HCl) or degradation of drug by specific enzyme i.e. also generated from micro organism (J.L. Slavin *et al.*)

Trimethazine dihydrochloride is the highly water soluble drug is prepared as three layer matrix table design as oral controlled drug delivery system gaur gum is utilized as potential carrier that control the release of drug from the carrier. (Y.S.R. Krishnaiah *et al.*)

one more example of the water soluble drug such as diltiazem hydrochloride oral controlled release drug delivery system compared study with marketed diltiazem Hcl table (DSR tablet) prepared on sustained release drug delivery system this matrix table is prepared from guar gum by utilizing the wet granulation method.(R. Lapasin *et al.*)

Guar Gum Extraction

The method applied is based on a procedure described by Cunha *et al.* with some modification. Weight approx 5-6g crude guar gum and it was treated with ethyl alcohol/absolute alcohol in an assembled Soxhlet apparatus this takes 3 days of complete extraction. The resulting product was hydrated with distilled water 500ml & agitating this mixture on magnetic stirrer with hot plate for about 13h. and thus it was centrifuged at 1500 rpm for 15 min.^[56,57] D. Wong *et al.* the resulting supernatant was precipitated by using acetone and thus strained off through nylon cloth & purified successively with ethyl alcohol & the dialyzed against for 3 days & refrigerated dried gum. (V.R. Sinha *et al.*)

KARAYA GUM

Karaya gum termed as sterculiyya gum or Indian gum tragacanth or Gond katira to get acquired from an exudate by trees.^[18] The karaya, is a vegetable edible gum belonging to family malvaceae, or Sterculiaceae genus sterculia gum (Anupama setial *et al.*), is the partially acetylated polymer of rhamnose, glucuronic acid, galactose hydrophilic natural gum like xanthan gum and karaya gum powder^[19] where employed as release controlling agent for the preparation of matrix tablet by using direct compressed method.

Caffeine & diclofenac sodium which have distinct solubility in water (aqueous) medium have been preferred for gum erosion hydration and candidate drug release studies by dissolution test apparatus basket dissolution test at two agitation speeds deduced that drug release from matrix prepared from combination of karaya gum and xanthan gum depend upon agitation, speed solubility & proportion of the candidate drug.

In the combination of karaya gum and xanthan gum product manufacture nearby the zero order drug release with the erosion system functioning presiding character especially in karaya gum matrices.^[18]

It was concluded that karaya gum is used as superior adhesive properties in the preparation of muco-adhesive tablet for buccal drug delivery system; than guar gum was accomplished to provide zero order drug release but concentration greater than 50%W/W may be essential for provide suitable sustained release drug delivery system. (Anupama setial *et al.*)

ALOVERAGEL

Alovera gel obtained from the aloevera leaves belonging to family *barbadensis*, investigated by isolating the exudates from alovera gel leaves this exudates have bitter in taste & yellow in colour & consist glycoside i.e. – major constituents & minor constituent are such as lipid, amino acid, protein, vitamins enzymes & various carbohydrates. (K.Subramanian *et al.*)

The major constituents is Arabinan, arabino rhamnogalatan, galactan, gluco-galactomannan & glycoranic acid have been founded in gel when this mucilage of povidone is combine together is used effectively in novel drug delivery system especially for sustained release of drug in sustained release drug delivery system.^[20]

The Extraction of gel from aloe leaves^{[21] [22]}

The leaves obtained from the aloe plant was rinsed with garden fresh distilled water the outer layer of leaves surface removed from the sharp knife or blade to build a fillet.^[22] The fillet was homogenized by employing the domestic mixer or mixer grinder.^[21] After then 60ml pulp was centrifuged. The charcoal was added to in the pulp to separate out all the fibers and crude gel present in aloe gel. For achieving the pure form of aloevera gel most essential methodology was used as. vaccum filtration method through the Whatsman filter paper.^[40]

INULIN

Inulin reported as polysaccharides obtained from the bulb *Dehlia* (*Inula helenium*) belonging to family; roots of *dendtion taraxacam officinale* (*compositae*) burdock.^{[23] [24]}

Inulin comprises combination of polymer & oliyomers that belong to the group of glucofraetans occur in plants such as garlic, onion & chicory inulin in combination with high degree of polymerization was used to prepare biodegradable.^[25]

ROSIN OR COLOPHONY

It is a solid state of resin acquired from pines & some other plants mostly conifer produced generated by boiling fresh liquid demolished the terpene, i.e. volatile liquid constituents.^[27]

Colophony (Resin) is a natural polymer ie extracted & isolated from pine tree (M.W of the colophony is about 400(Dalton)).^[28]

Fundamentally rosin is consist of a biotic & pimaric acid and has magnificent film forming properties matrix material in the formulation of tablet in sustained and controlled drug

delivery system^[27] it was demonstrate that on the basic of rosin contend for the formulation of hydrocortisone loaded nano particle, the release of model drug is slow.^[29,45]

The Extraction of colophony extract

Primarily, colophony resin was milled to (reduces size) to a coarse powder by employing the mixer (homogenizer) the about 200gm of colophony fine powder was soaked in 1000ml solvent i.e. methyl alcohol (methanol) for the preparation of extract. Then the resulting extract was allowed to kept or 24h., after which it was strained out by using muslin cloth.^[30,46] The filtrate was allowed to evaporated along with the addition of evaporator system.

HIBISCUS MUCILAGE

Mucilage obtained from hibiscus (*Hibiscus rosa sinensis*) belonging to family malvaceae.^[31] commonly named as cotton rose, muhagua, china rose, topography shoup growing to 7-12 feet height, having glossy, gloom green leaves produced throughout in India, the year.^[32,47]

Formulation of diclofenac sodium tablet by using mucilage obtained from hibiscus rosa-sinosis leaves^[32] it has excellent retardant activity for sustained release of candidate drug or model drug preparation of sustained release drug delivery system A mucilage have various number of physicochemical properties investigated in formulation of diclofenac sodium. (Madan *et al.*) the resulting tablet formulated from matrix show excellent uniformity, hardness & friability the swelling of this matrix tablet^[32] & their characteristic property of release rate in vitro showed that the mucilage from dried leaves of *Hibiscus rosa sinensis* can potentially be used in sustained drug release employed the mucilage followed zero order reaction kinetics.^[31]

Extraction procedure of mucilage from the hibiscus

Hibiscus rosa sinensis Linn. fresh leaves are gathered, cleaned with distill water to eliminate dirt and debris (Madan *et al.*) dried leaves are soaked for 5-6 hr. and the cooked for 30minutes before being kept side for 1 Hrs so that all the mucilage may be liberate in to distilled water. To detach the marc from the solution, the matter is compressed out of an eight fold muslin cloth. the mucilage found in the form of precipitate , acetone is incorporated in filtrate. By using the sieve no. 80 the mucilage is sieved and dried in a hot hair oven (dry heat sterilization) at a temperature of 50 degree Celsius before being stocked in desiccators for future application. (Madan *et al.*)

FENUGREEK MUCILAGE

Fenugreek seed, *Trigonella foenum-graecum* belonging to family Fabaceae^[34] having major constituents mucilage present in fenugreek seed accompanying natural gummy agent in the seed coating it does not dissolve in water & forms glutinous mass upon exposure to fluid & become efficient with finished exposure.^[35] The isolation of the husk from the seed is complete through reducing the size & suspending the seed in CHCl_3 (chloroform) before draining them. Oily phase is removed from the by using chloroform after extraction then it could be dried at 66.7% W/W supercellulose in retarding drug release compared to hypermeleose.^[34]

The Extraction of mucilage from fenugreek seed mucilage: (Ravi kumar *et al.*)

The mucilage was isolated according to the method described by Nosin & Vigneshwar (2014) firstly the 10gm fenugreek seed was soaked in 100ml distilled water (ie 1:10W/V) then keep it on magnetic stirrer with hotplate for 1h at 40°C. The viscous thickened solution was strained by using muslin cloth to eliminate the fiber i.e. unwanted material. Absolute ethanol/ethyl alcohol (99%) was incorporated in the ratio of 1:1 obtained a precipitate that contains mucilage in this then obtained mucilage as dried in hot air oven to prevent from hydration at given temperature 40-45 degree centigrade. The obtained dried mucilage was warehoused in air-tight or well closed container to prevent from any dirt & contamination.^[34]

TAMARIND GUM

Tamarind gum extracted from *Tamarindus indica*^[56,57] especially obtained from endosperm of seed part of tamarind family of this herb is called as tamarind xyloglucan.^[38,39,63] The tamarind kernel part of seed is employed for generating tamarind kernel powder, the following unit step involved in the solution of gum from seed selection, removal of coating from the seed, hammer milling, grinding & sieving etc gum from *Tamarindus indica* in ratio 3:1:1 is glucosyl xylosyl:galactosyl these are polysaccharide in nature.^[40-41]

Extraction procedure of gum from the tamarind: (Amelia *et al.*)

The gum extracted from the tamarind (kernel powder) i.e. easily available in market region.^[56,57,58] Firstly, weigh the twenty gram of desaturated tamarind seed powder was mixed with ~200 milliliter of distilled chilled water for preparing the slurry. Then slurry was cascaded into the 800 milliliter of the steaming distilled water accommodating of 0.2% citric acid. The whole solution was steaming for 20 min. with continuous stirring on the hot plate.^[41,63,64] A clear solution is achieved and this is kept for 24 hours (overnight) for obtaining proteins and fibers settle down at the bottom following which the solution is

centrifuge at 5000rpm for 20 minutes. (Amelia *et al*) Resulting supernatant liquid is segregated and poured in to the immoderate of absolute alcohol with continuous stirring (1:1). The obtained precipitate is rinse with 200ml of ethyl alcohol, diethyl ether acetone or / and petroleum ether. It will be properly dry at 50-60 degree Celsius for 10hrs. Dried polymer was converted in to powder form, sieved and housed in a desiccators as for as before further application.^[41]

FLAXSEED MUCILAGE

Flaxseed composed of notable cluster of gum or mucilage i.e. a hydrophilic colloid.^[42,43] Flaxseed mucilage principally arises in the outer most layer of hull.^[43] Flaxseed is well known to passes multiple medical benefits like sustain gastric emptying lower the cholesterol and enhance controlled level of glucose in the blood.^[44] Flaxseed mucilage reveal better water binding magnitude and rheological properties therefore flaxseed mucilage can be employed mostly as stabilizer, emulsifier in the formulation of novel drug delivery system.^[43,44,45]

Extraction procedure of mucilage from the flaxseed^[44]

Approximately, 10gram entire portion of flaxseed to be measured on the weighing balance and soaked in ~ 200milliliter of the distilled water, for making thick and viscous gel the amount of water to be reduced . Rigorously rinse the flaxseed with water to eliminate the any type of dirt or water to establish. In clean utensil incorporated the flaxseed with the distill water.^[44] Warm up the whole portion of mixture over the normal heat while stirring at intervals. The warmness will assist the mucilage to dissolve from the seed in to the distill water for the development of gel like steadiness.^[45] Occurrence of settle down and burning of forming mucilage is to be prohibited from continuous stirring the mixture, it take about 10-15 min. whenever combination has to be thickened and proceed to gel like consistency, It should be removed from the warming stage and mucilage is obtained by straining the mixture by using sieve no.40.

Application of plant based natural polymer in the novel drug delivery formulation

- 1. Pectin gum:** Used in the preparation of matrix tablets, encapsulation method, release of drug in the controlled manner in the body.
- 2. Guar gum:** Matrix tablet preparation, oral controlled drug delivery system and disintgrants.^[76,77,78]

3. **Karaya gum:** Mucoadhesive type tablet formulation, buccal drug delivery system, formulation of sustained release tablet. (Anupama setial *et al.*)
4. **Aloe gel:** Give Sustain release formulation along with other natural or synthetic polymer.
5. **Inulin:** Colon specific film formulation that prevent gastric and intestinal fluids.
6. **Colophony:** sustained and controlled release tablet matrix and nano-particle preparation.^[27,28,46]
7. **Hibiscus rosa- sinensis:** sustained release of drug and preparation of matrix tablet(Madan *et al.*)
8. **Fenugreek seed mucilage:** Used as disintegrant in combination with super disintegrants, fast- disintegrating tablet formulation.(Ravi Kumar *et al.*)
9. **Tamarind gum:** used as binder, stabilizers, gelling agent and thickening agent, that have muco-adhesive properties.^[56,57,58,63]
10. **Okara gum:** Used as a binder matrix tablet and sustain release drug formulation.
11. **Flaxseed mucilage:** Used as good binder, emulsifier, stabilizers and retard the release of drug from the matrix tablet, sustained release tablet formulation.^[48,49,50]

CONCLUSION

The application of only plant basis natural polymer for the formulation of novel drug delivery system is more essential and attractive than synthetic natural polymers in competition of readily available, non toxic chemical modification capabilities potentially biodegradable and minute exception, having compatible with body and employed formula. The majority of investigation on plant based polymer i.e. obtained from natural environment, applied in the formulation of novel drug delivery system, to enhance the efficiency, effectiveness, bio compatibility by extracting the mucilage / gum or resin from the various plant that is originated from around us. These are the extracted pant based natural polymer are in combination with other polymer or excipients improved the release of drug in a controlled and sustained or retard manner mainly in novel formulation. Such natural polymers are used as binding agent, emulsifier or emulsifying agent, stabilizers, and braking down capability (that fasten the release of Active pharmaceutical ingredients) and also for the preparation of matrix table and film coating tablet.

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